

LOCAL GOVERNMENT AUTONOMY AND EFFICIENT SERVICE DELIVERY AT THE GRASSROOT: A STUDY OF SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Anthony Bassey Wilson¹
Solomon Bassey Udofia²

^{1&2}Department of Political Science
College of Education, Afaha Nsit, Akwa Ibom State
¹abwilson65@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Local Government according to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria with amendments 2011 is accorded the status of an autonomous level/tier of government in the structural administrative configuration of the Nigerian Federal and is saddle with specific functions. Unfortunately, over the years, the administration of Local Government in Nigeria as an autonomous level/tier of government has been an issue of serious contention to well-meaning Nigerians¹ This paper therefore, is prompted by the need to critically examine the status of Local Government as an autonomous level/tier of government in Nigeria, especially in the doma'4n of service delivery to people at the grassroots. The study would focus attention on some selected Local Government councils chosen from the three (3) Senatorial Geo-political Zones of Akwa Ibom State; Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene as its case study. To guide the study, three (3) Null hypotheses bordering on the influence of periodic elections at the local government level, the continued operation of the state and Local Government joint account and the undue interference and encroachment of state government on the affairs of Local Government on Local Government Council's efficient service delivery to people at the grassroots. The survey/descriptive research design would be adopted to carry out the study, hence, the need to administer a structured questionnaire on the sample population of the study. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) would be adopted to analyze the data¹ The major findings of the study which intend to correlate on the influence of periodic elections at the Local Government level, the abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account and the non-interference and encroachment of state government on the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery at the grassroots. Based on the major findings of the study, among others recommendations, was that there is the need to accord the much desire autonomy to local government as a distinct level/tier of government in the Nigerian federation.

KEYWORDS: Local government, autonomy, grassroots, and efficient services

INTRODUCTION

The sovereign state Nigeria, is a federal state and is constitutionally divided into three levels/tiers of government with a federal/central government, thirty-six state governments and seven hundred and seventy- four local government councils. Each level of government is constitutionally saddled with specific functions (FGN: 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria with amendments 2011). Of all the levels/tiers of government, there is no gain saying the fact that the local government is the oldest level/tier of government in Nigeria. Indeed, long before the advent. of British colonial rule, indigenous Nigerian Societies had. their unique system of local administrations upon which the British colonial rule anchored the indirect rule system. The idea at the time according to Ola and Tonwe cited in Otoghile and Terkimbi (2014) was to preserve and use the authority of the local rulers, local institutions, traditions and customs rather than attempt to impose totally new and unfamiliar ideas on the local peoples.

An. in-depth analysis of the evolutionary trend of local administration/government in Nigeria revealed that between the 1930s and 1940s, local government operated under the platform of the Chief-in- Council and Chie in-and-Council. In the former, the Chief had the liberty accept or reject the advice of his Council whereas in the latter, the Chief had a Council who shared with the decision making authority. In the 1950s, elections were introduced into the local government system, in the East in 1950, in the West in 1952 and in the North in 1954. Gboyega (1987) argued that the institution of local government in Nigeria has undergone many changes. According to him, colonial rule, the local government reforms of the 1950s, the military coup of 1966 and the .t9ih local government reform all have very serious implications on the nature and character of local governments in Nigeria.

However, what have perhaps remained the most contentious issues confronting local government in Nigeria are the functional erosion as well as the over-bearing encroachment on the part of the state government on the activities of the local government, thereby undermining the imperatives for local government autonomy. It was due to this trend of affairs that the major thrust of the 1976 local government reform from the federal government was to neutralize these unhealthy dispositions and attitudes of state governments to local government councils in Nigeria.

The debate on local government as an autonomous level/tier of government in Nigeria has engaged the attention of scholars of local government administration and well-meaning Nigerians over the years. Indeed, the 1976 guidelines for Local Government Reform which specifically Viewed local government as a distinct level/tier of government that is mandated to be exercised through representative councils within defined areas has over the years been obliterated. Local government autonomy by the strength of the wordings of the 1976 Guidelines on Local Government Reform should be

Characterized by less interference or minimal control by higher levels of government (i.e the federal and state governments) on local administrative affairs, especially, in the areas of finance, staffing, financial responsibilities, policy initiation and implementation, etc. Unfortunately, despite the frantic efforts make by successive governments through various administrative reforms to make local government autonomous in Nigeria, local government still remained in practical terms, Far from being autonomous. Specifically, the intermittent disregard to the constitutional requirement that local government councils be constituted by a democratic elected council via periodic elections.

Indeed, apart from the fact that elections at the grassroots ensure people participation in local affairs, they equally make local representatives accountable to the people at the grassroots and to a large extent, promote the implementation of policies that are of local concern. This no doubt makes local government more responsive to the wishes and yearnings of the local people, the very act of which constitutes some degree of autonomy on its own. Nigeria experience of local government administration since 1976 however, revealed that most state governments have disregarded this constitutional requirement. and rather have resorted to the appointment of caretaker committee or sole administrators, as the case may be, to run the councils, One major implications of this practice is that local government officials remained dependent and answerable to higher levels of government instead of the local dwellers. This way, local government autonomy is seriously hampered.

Moreover, the absence of financial autonomy of local government which has continued to make focal government authorities financially dependent on the state and federal governments. Although, local government statutory allocation from the Federation Account- a major source of revenue to local government has been on the increase since 1976, while the federal government manages to remit some of the stipulated amount to local government, the state government which are equally mandated to remit in certain percentage of their internally generated revenue to local government in their domain rarely comply with his. Apart from this, the practice whereby federal government financial allocation to the local government are routed through the state governments 'and the establishment of a Joint: Account between the state and the local government has compounded the vital revenue meant for local government.

Furthermore, the decline on the internally generated revenue base of local government due 4to the combination of outright abolition of areas formally regarded as internal sources of local government revenue such as community tax, cattle tax, etc, and the continued encroachment on local government resources generating functions like motor parks, markets, etc. this scenarios discussed above have continued to make local governments economically unviable and therefore, unable to attain the status required of on an autonomous level/tier of government.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The concept of local government, like every other Social Sciences concept, not lend itself to a universally accepted definition, Accordingly, every scholar that attempts to conceptualized the concept, usually views it from his own perspective. Indeed, Imhanlahimi and Ikeayihe (2009) noted that the literature is very rich in the conceptualization of local government.

Accordingly, the United Nations Division of Public Administration cited in Awofeso (2000) views local government as:

...A political sub-division of a nation (or in a federal system, a state) which is constituted by law and has substantial control of local affairs, including the power to impose taxes or to exact labour for prescribed purposes. The governing body of such an entity elected or otherwise locally selected.

At a more theoretical level, Mawhood (1993) conceives local government as:

Bodies... separated by law.. (and have) local representatives (and,)... formal power to decide on a range of public matters... their right to make decisions is enhanced by the law and can only be altered by a new legislation. They have resources which subject to the stated limits are spent and invested at their discretion.

Corroborating on Mawhood's definition of what constitutes local government, Robson cited in Awoleso (2000) defines local government in the following words:

The conception of a territorial, non-sovereign community possessing the legal right and the necessary organ to regulate its own affairs. This in turn pre-supposes the existence of a local authority with power to act independently of external control as well as the participation of the local community in the administration of the local community in the administration of its own affairs.

From the plethora of all these definitions of a local government Awofeso (2000) argues that certain common features are discernible in these definitions, the absence of which disqualifies a local government as a real unit of government.

- i. An organized entity with distinct territorial boundaries functions
- ii. A corporate and legal personality with powers to perform some specified functions;
- iii. A system of representation through election of principal officers, effective citizen participation and in-built accountability; and
- iv. Substantial autonomy over finance and staffing with limited and complementary central control.

Perhaps, these common features informed the federal military government in the 1976 guidelines for local government reform to define local government as government at local level, exercised through representative council established by law to exercise specific powers within defined areas (FGN, 1976).

Similarly, the concept of local government autonomy is also not spared the multiplicity of definitions. Wolman and Goldsmith (1990), view local government autonomy in terms of politics and essentially view the concept as the local government's ability to have an independent impact on the welfare of the residents of the local jurisdiction. Boyne (1996) later expanded this definition by explicitly including local government powers to innovate, experiment and develop policies that can vary by jurisdiction. Boyne argues further that local government should have sufficient autonomy to compete with each other in terms of quality and quantity of service delivery. Two types of local autonomy appear to have been canvassed in the literature-absolute and adequate/relative autonomy. Scholars from the absolute school often argue that the autonomy of local governments is absolute and such, other levels of government should not intrude through whatever means, in their affairs. Flowing from this contention, Chaturvedi (2006) asserts that in local autonomy, the local body has financial and management autonomy to decide and determine its own course of action. Denial of autonomy can be based on some leaders who seek selfish interest (Peters and

Bassey, 2019). Mawhood (1993) straddles both schools when he insists that there is a relative separation of central and local spheres of government on the one hand, while on the other hand, he asserts that the central government should only monitor the activities of local government without intruding into their domains.

Awa (2006) assessing the views of these scholars opines that local government autonomy may be viewed as the amount of power granted to local governments by the state or central government. This power is expressed in terms of the functions assigned to them, the extent to which they are allowed to generate revenue by themselves, the source of other revenues and the supervision of expenditure, the supervision of local council deliberations by states representatives, the relation of local councils to extra-legal institution such as the town improvement unions and the traditional authority, etc.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Efficient-service school of thought the leading advocates in this school are William Mackenzie and Sharpe. The scholars in this school of thought argued that the purposes of local government are to provide services that are locally characterized to the people at the grassroots also to cater for the people and construct local roads, maintain law and order, provide water, build community health centre, etc for the people. It further notes that the essence of local government is to deliver services to the people at the grassroots. This school explained that since local government is the closest government to the people, it should be justified with its responsibilities.

William Mackenzie, (1954), in chukwuemeka, *et al* (2014) noted that service delivery to the local people is expected to pre-occupy the resources, power and time of the local government. This school main argument is that the existence of local government is to engender efficient-service delivery to the local dwellers (Kafle and Karkee, 2003). The theory stipulates that local governments exist to articulate and aggregate the interests and aspirations of the people for better and more efficient services. It also argues that what is central and important to the people is the knowledge and articulation of the problem confronting them and finding appropriate solutions to such problems; since the officials of the local government councils are indigenes of the areas, they are in a better position to understand the needs of the people and provide efficient services for their welfare. These have positioned the local for autonomy in term of financial allocation and political influence.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the survey/descriptive research design which involved the use of research instruments like questionnaire administration to elicit relevant data from the sample population. The study was conducted in selected Local Government Councils in Akwa Ibom State. However, the study concentrated on four (4) Local Government Councils in each senatorial zone-Uyo, Ikot Ekpene and Eket senatorial zones. The study respondents comprised of all senior administrative staff of the selected local government councils. The sample size for the study was four hundred (400). This sample size was chosen through the randomization sampling technique. Data were collected through administration of structured questionnaire on the sample size, and a major secondary data adopted for the study was the Federal republic of Nigeria Official Gazotte (19%). The researchers adopted frequency counts, tabular presentations and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) for the

analysis of data. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test all the hypotheses formulated to guide the study at 0.05 alpha levels in attempts to establish existing relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

RESULT

In this section, the data collected in the study are analysed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis (PPMC). This was done by applying the statistics to analyse the formulated hypotheses.

Test of hypothesis I

H_0 : Hypothesis one in the null form states that there is no significant influence of lack of periodic election at local government on local government council's efficient service delivery to people at grassroot in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 18 Contingency table for Hypothesis One, showing the influence of lack of periodic election at local government (X) on local government council's efficient service delivery (Y)

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
4	172	16	29,584	688
3	97	9	9,409	291
2	26	4	676	52
1	7	1	49	7
10	302	30	39,718	1038

$$\Sigma X = 10, \Sigma Y = 302, \Sigma X^2 = 30, \Sigma Y^2 = 39,718, \Sigma XY = 1038$$

The Pearson r calculated value = 0.97

To test for significance of the relationship between X and Y, the formula given as (see appendix). The result is stated as $r = 5.6 > df = 2 > p = .05 <= 0.95$; OR $r = 5.6 > 2 > 0.05 < 0.95$

This implies that r calculated value = 5.6 while the critical or table value = 0.95. With a co-efficient of 0.97, it means a strong and positive influence of lack of periodic election at the local government on local government efficient service delivery to the grassroot. Based on the rule of statistical decision which states that if the calculated value of a statistics is equal or greater than the critical value of the statistics, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, and vice versa, the (H_0) null hypothesis (hypothesis one) formulated in this study which argues that there is no significant influence of lack of periodic election at the local government on local government council's efficient service delivery to the people at grassroot in Akwa Ibom State is rejected and the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant influence of lack of periodic election at the local government on local government council's efficient service delivery to the people at grassroot in Akwa Ibom State is accepted.

Test of hypothesis II

H_0 : Hypothesis two in the null form states that there is no significant impact of abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 19 Contingency table for Hypothesis Two, showing the impact of abolition of state and local government joint account (X) on local government council's efficient service delivery (Y)

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
4	167	16	27,889	668
3	98	9	9,604	294
2	29	4	841	58
1	8	1	64	8
10	302	30	38,398	1028

$$\Sigma X = 10, \Sigma Y = 302, \Sigma X^2 = 30, \Sigma Y^2 = 38,398, \Sigma XY = 1028$$

The Pearson r calculated value = 0.97

To test for significance of the relationship between X and Y, the formula given as (see appendix). The result is stated as $r = 5.6 > df = 2 > p = .05 \leq 0.95$; OR $r = 5.6 > 2 > 0.05 < 0.95$

This implies that r calculated value = 5.6 while the critical or table value = 0.95. With a co-efficient of 0.97, it means a strong and positive impact of abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account on local government council's efficient service delivery. Based on the rule of statistical decision which states that if the calculated value of a statistics is equal or greater than the critical value of the statistics, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, and vice versa, the (H_0) null hypothesis formulated in this study which argues that there is no significant impact of abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom state is rejected and the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant impact of abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State is accepted.

Test of hypothesis III

H_0 : Hypothesis three in the null form states that there is no significant impact of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 20 Contingency table for hypothesis three, showing the impact of undue interference of state government in the affairs of local government (X) on local government council's efficient service delivery (Y)

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
4	128	16	16,384	512
3	73	9	5,329	219
2	64	4	4096	128
1	37	1	1369	37
10	302	30	27,178	896

$$\Sigma X = 10, \Sigma Y = 302, \Sigma X^2 = 30, \Sigma Y^2 = 27,178, \Sigma XY = 896$$

The Pearson r calculated value = 0.95

To test for significance of the relationship between X and Y, the formula given as (see appendix). The result is stated as $r = 5.6 > df = 2 > p = .05 <= 0.95$; OR $r = 5.6 > 2 > 0.05 < 0.95$

This implies that r calculated value = 4.2 while the critical or table value = 0.95. With a co-efficient of 0.95, it means a strong and positive impact of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery. Based on the rule of statistical decision which states that if the calculated value of a statistics is equal or greater than the critical value of the statistics, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, and vice versa, the (H_0) null hypothesis formulated in this study which argues that there is no significant impact of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State is rejected and the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant impact of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State is accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The local government council is shouldered with the responsibility of taking the activities of government to the people at the grassroots level. This responsibility is based on its roles in harnessing, coordinating, organizing and administering factors or components of development at the local government level toward efficient service delivery to the people at the grassroots level. The factors or components of developments include human labour, materials resources, and natural resources. In this study, findings were made and are summarized under the following sub-headings:

i. Influence of lack periodic election at Local Government on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State

The result of the test of hypothesis on the impact of lack of periodic election at local government on local government council's efficient service delivery to people at grassroots in Akwa Ibom State yielded a value of 0.97. The interpretation of this is that there is a highly significant relationship between lack of periodic election at local government and local government council's efficient service delivery to people at grassroots in Akwa Ibom State. The finding of this research is supported by the position of Awofeso (2000), who posited that a common feature of a local government should be a system of representation through election of principal officers, effective citizen participation and in-built accountability. This therefore can be said that according to the finding of this research study, periodic election is found to be a necessary characteristic which make a local government area a government unit at the grassroots level, elected by the people of the council's area for effective representation through closeness and knowledge of the elected officers. The 1976 guidelines for local government reform by the then federal military government which stated that as the local government as government at the local level, should exercise through representative councils established by law to exercise specific powers within defined areas.

ii. Impact of abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State

The result of the test of hypothesis on the impact of abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account on local government council's efficient service

delivery in Akwa Ibom State yielded a value of 0.9776. The interpretation of this is that there is a highly significant relationship between abolition of the operation of the state and local government joint account and local government council's efficient service delivery to the grassroot people in Akwa Ibom State. The finding of this research is supported by the works of Chaturvedi (2006) who asserts that in local autonomy, the local body has financial and management autonomy to decide and determine its own course of action. Mawhood (1993) in his analysis of findings from his study asserted that there is a relative separation of central and local spheres of government, which should allow for separation of account for effective and efficient delivery of the local government to the people at the grassroot.

iii. Impact of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State

The result of the text of hypothesis on the impact of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government on local government council's efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State yielded a value of 0.9531. The interpretation of this is that there is a highly significant relationship between undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government, and local government council's efficient service delivery to the people at the grassroot in Akwa Ibom State. The finding is given credence by Mawhood (1993) who asserts that the central government should only monitor the activities of local government without intruding into their domains. Chaturvedi (2006) also support the finding of this study through his assertion that local government should have autonomy which should allow it to decide and determine its own course of action. Local government autonomy according to this findings is the withdrawal of undue interference and encroachment of state government in the affairs of local government council.

CONCLUSIONS

Local government councils are expected to take the activities of government to the people at the grassroots. As much is expected from other tiers of government, there are much expected from the local government by the people at the local level or grassroot. These expectations can only be attained through efficient service delivery of the members of the local government council who are looked upon as the government to the grassroot people. The failure of the local government council is considered as failure of all other tiers of government. For the local government not to fail there is need for local government autonomy which reduces undue interference of the state in the local government affairs, abolition of state and local government joint account, and a periodic election of officers of the local government area will enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the local government councils.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made from the findings of this work research:

- i. There is need to accord the much desire autonomy to local government as a distinct level/tier of government in Nigerian federation.
- ii. There should be obliteration of state and local government joint account in order to

- give local government councils the needed financial autonomy.
- iii. There should be abolition of caretaker committees in the local government to give way to election of officers of council which will enhance accountability of officers.

REFERENCES

- Awa, E. (2006), 'Democracy in Nigeria: A political scientist View' 'n Oyediran, O. (ed) Governance and Development in Nigeria, Ibadan: Agbo Arco Publishers
- Awofeso, Olu (2000), "Nigerian Youth and Democratic Stability in the New Millennium: A SocioPsychological Analysis", *Journal of Education and Society*, University of Uyo, Vol.3
- Chaturvedi, A. K. (2006). Dictionary of Political Science. New Delhi: Academic Publishers.
- Chukwuemeka, E., Ugwuanyi, B. I, Okolo, P. and Onuoha, C. E. (2014). Nigeria Local Government: A Discourse on the Theoretical Imperatives in a Governmental System. *African Review An International Multidisciplinary Journal*, Vol. 8 (2), Serial No. 33. Pp 305-324.
- Gboyega, A. (1987). Political Values and Local Government in Nigeria. Ibadan: Malthouse Press Limited.
- Imhanlahimi, J. E. and Ikeanyibe, M. O. (2009). Local Government Autonomy and Development of Localities in Nigeria: Issues, Problems and Suggestions. *Global Journal of Social Sciences* 8(2)
- Kafle, S. and Karke, K. (2003). "Towards Ideal Local Government: Strengthening Participatory Development". Unpublished Memoir.
- Mawhood, P. (1993). Decentralisation: the Concept and Practice in Mawhood P. Local Government in the Third World: Experience of Decentralisation in Tropical Africa, Pretoria: The Africa Institute of South Africa.
- Otoghile, A. and Terkimbi, E. (2014) Local Government Administration and Development: A Survey of Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria. *International Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia* Vol. 5 (3), 148-156
- Peters, M. I. and Aniekan E. Bassey (2019). Complicating Social Order in the Rural Areas of Akwa Ibom State. *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*. Volume 17 Number, 2: 112 – 125
- Wolman, H. and Goldsmith, M. (1990). Local autonomy as a Meaningful Analytic Concept Comparing Local Government in the United States and the United Kingdom. *Urban Affairs Review*. 26. 3-27. 10.1177/004208169002600101.